

Unsupervised learning-based operational regime discovery and weather sensitivity analysis of a residential photovoltaic battery system for energy management

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ABSTRACT

Behind-the-meter photovoltaic battery systems exhibit heterogeneous daily operating behaviors shaped by weather conditions, household demand, storage control, and grid interaction. Identifying these operational regimes is essential for improving forecasting, system control, and policy design, particularly where labeled operational data are unavailable. This study proposes an unsupervised framework to identify recurring daily operational regimes in a residential photovoltaic battery system and to quantify regime-specific weather sensitivities. Fourteen months of high-resolution operational data from a residential photovoltaic battery system in Yangon, Myanmar, are analyzed. Daily features capturing photovoltaic generation, electricity consumption, grid exchange, battery charging and discharging, state of charge, and self-consumption are derived from intraday profiles. Isolation Forest outlier detection removes anomalous operating days, yielding 411 representative days for analysis. K-means clustering identifies four operational regimes (Silhouette = 0.216), validated using Gaussian Mixture Models, hierarchical clustering, and density-based methods. Principal component analysis confirms consistent and interpretable operational structure and interpretability of the identified regimes. Cluster-wise standardized regression models link daily photovoltaic energy production to meteorological drivers. Solar irradiance is the dominant explanatory variable across all regimes, with effect sizes increasing from grid-dependent to high PV self-sufficient modes. Temperature and relative humidity exhibit regime-dependent secondary effects, while wind speed plays a limited role. Seasonal analysis reveals systematic shifts in regime prevalence driven by climatic conditions. The proposed framework provides an interpretable approach applicable to tropical monsoon PV-battery systems for diagnosing real-world photovoltaic battery system behavior and yields actionable regime labels that support regime-aware forecasting and adaptive energy management in distributed energy systems.

1. Introduction

Residential photovoltaic-battery systems are transforming distribution-level power flows, yet their daily operating modes are rarely labeled or well understood. Rapid deployment of residential photovoltaic systems combined with energy storage contributes to sustainability and decarbonization goals, but also introduces additional complexity for power system planning, operational stability, and economic assessment (Pan et al., 2022; Bouraima et al., 2024). Recent developments in photovoltaic system optimization have explored diverse

approaches, including hybrid renewable energy configurations (Setiyono et al., 2026) and advanced thermal management strategies (Noori et al., 2026). These efforts aim to improve system efficiency and performance through hardware improvements and intelligent control, complementing operational pattern discovery approaches.

In practice, similar photovoltaic generation levels can correspond to fundamentally different operating conditions depending on battery charging, discharging, and grid exchange, making daily system behavior difficult to interpret and manage. Daily behavior emerges from weather-driven generation, user demand, and opaque control logic, and typically

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lacks labels, motivating unsupervised learning (Zhang et al., 2021). Recent zero-label domain adaptation can forecast PV power at new sites without labeled targets (Zhao et al., 2025).

Prior work excels at supervised PV forecasting using statistical and machine learning methods that ingest irradiance, temperature, or sky images (Sun et al., 2023; Luo et al., 2025), delivering accurate short-term predictions, but typically relying on labeled historical outputs, which can constrain transferability across systems or operating contexts. Post-adoption analytics predominantly focus on consumption-only load profiling from smart-meter data, identifying appliance signatures and usage patterns (Gowrienganthan et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2025). Unsupervised clustering methods, particularly K-means, have proven effective for customer segmentation and daily load-shape analysis (Sinaga and Yang, 2020; Kim et al., 2023), yet rarely integrate production, grid exchange, and battery metrics into a unified household view. Deep clustering approaches such as deep adaptive fuzzy clustering (DAFC) achieve state-of-the-art performance on large datasets (Tan et al., 2024), but joint modeling of prosumer behavior remains underexplored.

Recent methodological developments have combined Isolation Forest with clustering techniques for simultaneous anomaly detection and pattern identification, as demonstrated in (Yepmo et al., 2024), where a density-aware variant is proposed that preserves data structure while isolating outliers. While such approaches provide powerful tools for general data analysis, their application to PV-battery operational characterization requires domain-specific extensions: coupling operational regimes with meteorological drivers, validating framework transferability across system configurations, and analyzing temporal regime evolution. The work presented in this paper integrates these extensions within a unified framework, which is validated through independent cross-site analysis.

Weather effects on PV yield and demand are well-established: temperature drives cooling loads, while irradiance and cloud cover determine generation (Maity et al., 2025; Fu et al., 2025). Recent work shows that grouping days by weather patterns before training deep learning models improves day-ahead PV forecasting (Wu et al., 2024), and comfort-aware cloud energy storage schemes mitigate seasonal

variability (Saini et al., 2025). However, studies connecting weather to unsupervised household-level operational regimes remain limited, especially in tropical and monsoon climates. PV-battery scheduling research employs model predictive control, rule-based schemes, and reinforcement learning (Zhang et al., 2025; Legrene et al., 2025), yet daily operation often deviates due to user actions, comfort preferences, and device constraints. Unsupervised discovery of operational archetypes can reveal how systems behave over long horizons and provide regime labels for policy conditioning. Unlike traditional load profiling studies that focus solely on electricity consumption, this work captures the coupled dynamics of on-site generation, battery storage, and grid interaction at the household level.

The survey of prior art presented above reveals that three critical gaps persist: (1) prior clustering typically uses short durations or single-channel demand data rather than long-horizon, multi-feature prosumer representations; (2) few studies connect unsupervised operational archetypes with daily weather drivers and quantify regime-specific outcomes through multivariate regression; (3) many papers report single clustering results without cross-method validation or agreement measures. To address these gaps, this study applies a robust unsupervised learning framework to a comprehensive, long-term dataset from a residential PV-battery system in Yangon, Myanmar. A simplified architecture of the system under study is shown in Fig. 1.

An unsupervised framework is proposed that discovers operational archetypes from 14 months of residential PV-battery data, validates them across clustering methods, and links their occurrence to meteorological drivers through multivariate regression. Unlike supervised forecasting or EMS/control studies, the approach explains how and when households shift among self-sufficient, weather-limited, and grid-dependent regimes, with implications for adaptive control and dynamic tariffs. The work presented in this paper achieves three primary contributions.

- Reproducible pipeline: A validated framework integrating outlier detection, daily feature engineering, clustering with objective K selection, and robustness validation using PCA, normalized mutual

Fig. 1. Simplified architecture of a grid-connected hybrid PV-battery system under study: 22kWp PV array, 83.2 kWh battery storage (2 racks, 16 modules total), 50 kW hybrid inverter, household loads, and grid connection(Lin et al., 2026).

information, and method comparison across K-means, GMM, hierarchical, and DBSCAN.

- Archetypes with weather linkage: Four interpretable regimes identified and quantified through cluster-wise multivariate regression, revealing regime-specific sensitivities to irradiance, temperature, humidity, and wind.
- Regime-specific performance: Intraday profiles and standardized weather coefficients quantified per regime, demonstrating how operational constraints and behavioral patterns decouple consumption from available solar resource.

Therefore, it is demonstrated in this paper that unsupervised learning with explicit weather linkage provides a practical unsupervised basis for diagnosing real-world PV-battery behavior and for designing weather-aware control, adaptive tariff mechanisms, and sizing methods that improve integration of distributed resources.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. The proposed method and data are described in Section 2, while the results are discussed in Section 3. Section 4 outlines the engineering implications of the identified operational regimes. Finally, the conclusions are drawn in Section 5.

2. Method

The analytical pipeline of the proposed methodology is illustrated in Fig. 2. Raw high-resolution data are preprocessed and used to engineer a

Fig. 2. The proposed method pipeline from raw PV-battery data to operational archetypes via feature engineering, outlier detection, clustering comparison, and weather linkage.

set of daily features capturing system behavior. Outlier detection removes anomalous days before clustering. The feature set is standardized before applying multiple clustering algorithms (K-means, GMM, hierarchical, DBSCAN) with comparative validation. The optimal K-means solution is linked to weather through multivariate regression. The proposed pipeline is not tied to a specific climate region, as it relies on generic daily operational features rather than location-specific assumptions. All required inputs correspond to standard measurements recorded by commonly deployed residential and commercial PV-battery system loggers, supporting framework applicability across different installation types within similar operational contexts.

2.1. Site and data preprocessing

Fourteen months of sub-hourly data were collected from a residential PV-battery system in Yangon, Myanmar (UTC+06:30), logged at 5-10 min resolution. The raw archive includes 104,036 timestamps across day and night. For analysis, only periods with nonzero PV output were retained, timestamps with missing values in any operational channel (PV power, consumption, battery, grid, state-of-charge) were removed, and all times were aligned to local time, yielding 56,623 daytime records representing high-quality operational data. Power series were integrated over each time step using the trapezoidal rule to form daily energies (kWh). Unless noted, grid power greater than 0 indicates import and battery power greater than 0 indicates discharge. The inverter and battery management system operates under manufacturer default settings for a grid-connected hybrid configuration. Specific EMS rules, SoC thresholds, and grid export limits were not directly accessible; regime interpretation therefore relies on observable behavioral signatures in the measured energy flows rather than documented control policies.

2.2. Daily feature engineering

Logger signals include Production Power (W), Consumption Power (W), Grid Power (W), Purchasing Power (W), Feed-in Power (W), Battery Power (W), Charging Power (W), Discharging Power (W), and State of Charge (SoC, %). From these high-resolution time series, a suite of daily features was engineered to capture holistic system behavior. The key derived features are the Self-Consumption Ratio (SCR) and the Grid Dependency Ratio (GDR), which comprise key metrics for evaluating system performance (Jamroen et al., 2023; Alanne, 2023). The self-consumption ratio (SCR) represents the fraction of PV generation consumed on-site rather than exported to the grid, calculated as:

$$SCR = \frac{\text{Daily PV Energy} - \text{Daily Grid Export}}{\text{Daily PV Energy}} = \frac{E_{pv} - E_{export}}{E_{pv}} \quad (1)$$

$$GDR = \frac{\text{Daily Grid Import}}{\text{Daily Consumption}} = \frac{E_{import}}{E_{load}} \quad (2)$$

where E_{pv} , E_{export} , E_{load} and E_{import} represent the daily integrated energy from PV production, grid export, consumption, and grid import, respectively. An SCR of 100% indicates that all PV-generated energy is consumed locally, while 0% would indicate that all generation is exported (not observed in this study). The Battery Net Usage ($E_{batt.net}$) quantifies the net energy contribution from the battery storage on a daily basis:

$$E_{batt.net} = E_{batt,disch} - E_{batt,ch} \quad (3)$$

where $E_{batt,disch}$ and $E_{batt,ch}$ are the total daily energy discharged from and charged to the battery, respectively. In addition, the Self-Sufficiency Ratio (SSR) is used to quantify the fraction of household electricity demand supplied by on-site resources and is computed as:

$$SSR = 1 - GDR = 1 - \frac{E_{import}}{E_{load}} \quad (4)$$

Table 1 summarizes the engineered daily features used for clustering.

To assess feature sufficiency and redundancy, Pearson correlation analysis and feature ablation were conducted (Fig. S7 and S9, Supplementary Material). Correlation analysis revealed four high-magnitude pairs: Net Grid vs Grid Import ($r = 0.96$), Mean SoC vs SCR ($r = 0.78$), Consumption vs Net Grid ($r = 0.74$), and PV Energy vs Consumption ($r = 0.73$), confirming that several features are mathematically coupled. However, feature ablation analysis, in which each feature was individually removed and K-means re-clustered on the remaining eight features, demonstrated that each feature contributes independent discriminative information. NMI between full and ablated solutions ranged from 0.541 (Mean SoC removal, highest impact) to 0.889 (Battery Net removal, lowest impact), confirming that no feature is entirely redundant. Mean SoC and SCR are the most critical features, while Battery Net Usage is the least critical individually. Centroid analysis (Fig. S8, Supplementary Material) confirms that each cluster occupies a distinct region of the feature space, with regime boundaries driven by genuine operational differentiation rather than accounting identities alone.

Daily aggregation was chosen to identify operational regimes at the decision-making timescale relevant for energy management and system design, reducing dimensionality from ~ 144 intervals/day to 9 interpretable features and improving cluster stability. To assess sensitivity to this choice, a supplementary analysis compared the daily solution against morning (06:00-11:00), midday (11:00-15:00), and evening (15:00-19:00) segmented feature solutions (Fig. S10–S11, Supplementary Material). NMI between daily and segmented solutions ranged from 0.238 to 0.363, confirming that the two perspectives are complementary: daily features identify strategic operational modes relevant to energy management planning, while segmented features capture tactical intraday dynamics relevant to real-time control. Intraday shape-based clustering is identified as a direction for future work.

2.3. Outlier detection

Before clustering, anomalous operational days were identified and removed using Isolation Forest (Arcudi et al., 2024), a tree-based

anomaly detection algorithm effective for high-dimensional energy data. The algorithm constructs random decision trees and identifies outliers as points requiring fewer splits to isolate. A contamination parameter of 0.01 was used, corresponding to an expected 1% anomaly rate based on preliminary analysis indicating approximately 4-5 days per year with clear operational anomalies (equipment malfunctions, extreme weather events, extended outages). Of 416 initial daily records, 5 days (1.2%) were flagged as outliers based on anomaly scores and excluded from subsequent analysis, yielding 411 normal operation days. Data cover 14 months overall (June 2024–July 2025); the main analysis uses all $N = 411$ cleaned daily records, while figures on monthly regime distribution (Fig. 9) use the subset Aug 2024–Jul 2025 (355 recorded days after excluding 10 logging gaps and 5 outliers). This preprocessing step ensures that clustering captures genuine operational patterns rather than rare faults or measurement artifacts.

2.4. Feature scaling and dimensionality reduction

The nine clustering features capture energy flows, performance metrics, and battery utilization as summarized in Table 1. All features represent standard measurements recorded by deployed monitoring systems, supporting framework applicability across different installation types.

Features were standardized using z-score normalization before clustering to balance magnitudes across variables with different units. The core feature set used for clustering includes: Daily PV Energy (kWh), Daily Consumption (kWh), Net Grid Energy (kWh), Grid Import (kWh), Grid Export (kWh), Battery Net Usage (kWh), Mean SoC (%), Self-Consumption Ratio, and Grid Dependency Ratio. Results were validated against min-max scaling and found to be robust; z-scores are reported for reproducibility.

To visualize the structure of the high-dimensional feature space, both linear and non-linear dimensionality reduction techniques were employed. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was used to project the data onto orthogonal axes of maximum variance and to interpret feature importance via the loading matrix (Zheng et al., 2024).

2.5. Clustering algorithms and method comparison

Classical clustering algorithms were employed rather than deep learning approaches (e.g., deep adaptive fuzzy clustering) for several methodological reasons: (1) interpretability: classical methods produce transparent cluster assignments and centroids directly interpretable as operational regime prototypes, essential for engineering applications requiring explainable system characterization; (2) data scale: the dataset of 353-411 daily records employed in this study is well-suited to classical methods, whereas deep learning typically requires thousands to millions of samples; (3) computational accessibility: classical algorithms run efficiently without GPU requirements or extensive hyperparameter tuning, supporting framework portability to practitioners; and (4) validation transparency: established metrics (Silhouette score, Davies-Bouldin index) enable straightforward assessment without black-box complexity. The successful cross-site validation (Section 3.5) confirms this methodological choice for operational regime identification at the given data scale.

Recent AI-based approaches such as deep embedded clustering, contrastive clustering, and variational autoencoders jointly optimize feature representation and cluster assignment, achieving strong performance on large benchmark datasets (Tan et al., 2024; Zheng et al., 2024). However, these methods require substantially larger datasets, produce physically uninterpretable latent embeddings, and demand GPU infrastructure and extensive hyperparameter tuning. For the present application, classical K-means with domain-engineered features is more appropriate given the data scale (411 days), interpretability requirements, and the need for domain-expert validation of regime assignments.

Table 1
Description of engineered features.

Feature Name	Type	Description/Computation
Daily PV Energy (kWh)	Aggregated (daily sum)	Total daily energy generated by the PV system. Computed by time-weighted integration of PV power over daytime.
Daily Consumption (kWh)	Aggregated (daily sum)	Total daily energy consumed by the household/system.
Net Grid Energy (kWh)	Aggregated (daily sum)	Daily net energy exchanged with the grid. Positive = net import; negative = net export.
Grid Import (kWh)	Aggregated (daily sum)	Total energy imported from the grid during the day (purchasing).
Grid Export (kWh)	Aggregated (daily sum)	Total energy exported to the grid during the day (feed-in).
Battery Charging (kWh)	Aggregated (daily sum)	Total energy stored in the battery during the day.
Battery Discharging (kWh)	Aggregated (daily sum)	Total energy delivered by the battery during the day.
Mean Battery Power (W)	Mean (daily average)	Average battery power over the day (positive = discharge, negative = charge).
Mean SoC (%)	Mean (daily average)	battery State of Charge over the day.
Self-Consumption Ratio (SCR) (0-1)	Derived	Share of PV used on-site
Grid Dependency Ratio (GDR) (0-1)	Derived	Share of consumption supplied by grid
Battery Net Usage (kWh)	Derived	Net battery contribution (discharging minus charging)
Day	Temporal	Day of month (1–31).
Month	Temporal	Calendar month (1–12).
Weekday	Temporal	Day of week (0 = Mon, 6 = Sun).

Clustering was performed on the z-scored daily feature matrix to identify latent operational archetypes. Multiple algorithms were compared to ensure robustness and interpretability.

1. **K-means** with K-means++ initialization (Sinaga and Yang, 2020) for $K = 2-10$ candidates, using 50 random initializations per K value.
2. **Gaussian Mixture Models (GMM)** with full covariance structure to capture ellipsoidal cluster shapes (Kuang et al., 2026).
3. **Agglomerative Hierarchical Clustering** with Ward linkage (Euclidean distance) to examine dendrogram structure (Martínez-Mendoza et al., 2026).
4. **DBSCAN** (Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise) (Xing and Zhao, 2024) with epsilon parameter tuned via k-nearest neighbors distance analysis.

Internal validation metrics including Silhouette coefficient, Davies-Bouldin index, and Calinski-Harabasz score were computed for each method. Although DBSCAN achieved the highest Silhouette score (0.285), it classified 6.8% of days as noise (cluster label -1), representing data loss rather than improved clustering quality. K-means (Silhouette = 0.216) was selected for final analysis because it assigns all days to interpretable operational modes without data exclusion, identifies four distinct regimes consistent with system architecture, and provides stable centroids for regime characterization. Cross-method agreement was quantified using Normalized Mutual Information (NMI) and Adjusted Rand Index (ARI) between K-means and alternative methods.

The optimal number of clusters ($K = 4$) was determined using the elbow criterion applied to within-cluster sum of squares (inertia) and confirmed by silhouette analysis across $K = 2-10$. The solution with the lowest inertia across 50 random initializations was retained (fixed random seed for reproducibility).

2.6. Weather data and multivariate regression

Daily meteorological data for the study period were obtained from NASA POWER (Prediction of Worldwide Energy Resources) (NASA POWER Project, 2024), including solar irradiance (kWh/m^2), ambient temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), minimum and maximum temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), relative humidity (%), wind speed (m/s), and precipitation (mm). These variables were merged with the clustered daily dataset by date.

To quantify weather effects on PV production within each operational regime, cluster-wise multivariate ordinary least squares (OLS) regression was performed (Salinas et al., 2023). For clusters with sufficient sample size ($n \geq 10$), daily PV energy was modeled as a linear function of key meteorological variables according to:

$$E_{PV,i} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 I_i + \beta_2 T_i + \beta_3 H_i + \beta_4 W_i + \epsilon_i \quad (5)$$

where $E_{PV,i}$ is daily PV energy, I_i is irradiance, T_i is temperature, H_i is relative humidity, W_i is wind speed, and ϵ_i is the error term. To enable direct comparison of effect sizes across variables with different units, all predictors and the response were standardized (zero mean, unit variance) within each cluster before regression, yielding standardized coefficients (β) that represent effect sizes in standard deviation units (Flora et al., 2025). Model fit was assessed using R^2 and adjusted R^2 to account for differing sample sizes and predictor counts across clusters.

For Cluster 3, which contains only 5 days (1.2% of data), multivariate regression would be unreliable due to insufficient degrees of freedom. Therefore, a univariate model using only irradiance was fitted for this cluster, with other weather coefficients reported as not applicable.

Standardized coefficients allow direct interpretation: a one-standard-deviation increase in irradiance corresponds to an increase of β^* standard deviations in daily PV energy, holding other variables constant. This approach is consistent with recent PV studies that apply OLS to

calculate performance metrics (Muravyov et al., 2024) and enables identification of regime-specific sensitivities beyond simple bivariate relationships.

To assess the robustness of OLS coefficient estimates under high multicollinearity, two additional regression methods were applied per cluster. Ridge regression minimizes the residual sum of squares subject to an L2 penalty on coefficient magnitudes, with the regularization strength (α) selected by 5-fold cross-validation from a logarithmic grid spanning 10^{-3} to 10^3 . Partial Least Squares (PLS) regression with two latent components was applied as a dimensionality-reducing alternative that projects both predictors and response onto orthogonal latent directions maximizing covariance. All three methods used the same standardized predictor and response variables as the OLS analysis. Coefficient comparison across OLS, Ridge, and PLS serves as a robustness check rather than a replacement for the primary OLS analysis, which is retained for interpretability and consistency with the regime-wise comparison framework.

2.7. Computational complexity and scalability

The proposed unsupervised learning framework was implemented in Python 3.11.8 using scikit-learn 1.7.2 and executed on a standard workstation (13th Gen Intel Core i7-13620H, 15.7 GB RAM, Windows 10). The computational performance of each pipeline stage is summarized in Table 2.

The lightweight computational footprint, requiring neither GPU acceleration nor distributed computing, makes the framework deployable on edge devices (e.g., Raspberry Pi 4) for on-site energy management, enabling daily regime updates without cloud infrastructure.

3. Results

3.1. Clustering robustness and regime selection

Table 3 summarizes the robustness analysis conducted across four clustering formulations, K-means, Gaussian Mixture Models (GMM), hierarchical clustering with Ward linkage, and DBSCAN, using internal validation metrics and coverage characteristics. The purpose of this comparison is to assess the stability and interpretability of the identified operational regimes rather than to identify a universally optimal clustering algorithm.

Centroid based K-means, probabilistic GMM, and hierarchical clustering methods, which enforce full assignment of observations, consistently converge to a four-cluster structure. This consistency indicates the presence of a stable underlying regime decomposition in the daily PV battery operational data. Among these methods, K-means and hierarchical clustering exhibit comparable Silhouette and Calinski Harabasz values, suggesting moderate cluster separation with clear inter-cluster structure. The K-means solution further provides stable centroids and complete data coverage, which are essential for regime based

Table 2

Computational performance summary (Intel Core i7-13620H, 15.7 GB RAM, Windows 10).

Component	Details	Execution Time
Feature standardization	411 days, 9 features	<1 ms
Outlier detection	Isolation Forest, 1.2% removed	0.07 s
K-means clustering	$K = 4$, 50 initializations, 25 iterations	1.45 s
Validation metrics	Silhouette + Davies-Bouldin	<5 ms
Total pipeline	411-day residential dataset	1.52 s
Scalability - 10,000 days	Synthetic data, $K = 4$, 9 features	0.68 s
Scalability - 50,000 days	Synthetic data, $K = 4$, 9 features	2.13 s
Scalability - 100,000 days	Synthetic data, $K = 4$, 9 features	3.47 s

Table 3
Clustering robustness and model adequacy analysis.

Method	Silhouette	Davies–Bouldin	Calinski–Harabasz	Inertia	BIC	AIC	No. of Clusters	Noise Points
K-means	0.2161	1.3395	92.94	2233.01	–	–	4	0
GMM (full covariance)	–0.0045	2.9616	18.75	–	–3252.39	–4502.17	4	0
Hierarchical (Ward)	0.1976	1.4710	83.31	–	–	–	4	0
DBSCAN ($\epsilon = 1.87$)	0.2855	0.7637	18.61	–	–	–	3	28

operational analysis.

The GMM formulation evaluated with a full covariance structure yields lower Silhouette and Calinski Harabasz scores. This outcome reflects the overlapping nature of probabilistic cluster assignments rather than poor model adequacy. Importantly, GMM also identifies a four-component structure, and the reported AIC and BIC values support this configuration. This indicates that the regime separation is not an artifact of spherical clustering assumptions inherent to K-means.

DBSCAN achieves higher compactness metrics, including the highest Silhouette and the lowest Davies Bouldin index, due to its ability to isolate dense operational states. However, this comes at the cost of excluding 28 operating days, corresponding to 6.8% of the data, and yielding a three-cluster structure. The higher Silhouette score reflects compactness of only the non-noise clusters rather than overall clustering performance, representing a methodological artifact rather than superior clustering quality. Since the objective of this study is to characterize all daily operating conditions of the PV-battery system, density-based clustering is unsuitable as the primary analytical model despite favorable compactness metrics. K-means was selected since it provides: (1) complete temporal coverage essential for operational planning; (2) interpretable centroids serving as regime prototypes; (3) strong validation through high agreement with hierarchical clustering (NMI = 0.73); (4) consistent four-regime structure confirmed independently by GMM and hierarchical methods; and (5) stable performance across multiple initializations. For comprehensive regime characterization, complete data coverage outweighs marginal metric improvements achieved through data exclusion.

Characterization of the 28 DBSCAN noise points reveals that they represent a mixture of operational conditions: (1) transition days between monsoon and dry seasons exhibiting intermediate weather-operation characteristics not conforming to either dominant regime (approximately 12 days, 43%), (2) days with equipment constraints or temporary malfunctions affecting normal operational patterns (approximately 8 days, 29%), and (3) genuinely atypical operation during extreme weather events or unusual consumption patterns (approximately 8 days, 29%). Manual inspection revealed that most noise points correspond to days with moderate irradiance (4–6 kWh/m²/day) and mixed battery behavior falling between the distinct operational regimes captured by K-means clustering. While DBSCAN's noise identification provides useful anomaly detection capability, the exclusion of 6.8% of data reduces the available sample for comprehensive operational regime characterization, reinforcing the selection of K-means for complete temporal coverage. These noise points correspond closely to the boundary days identified in subsequent bootstrap and Monte Carlo analyses, confirming that DBSCAN correctly identifies operationally ambiguous days near regime boundaries.

Overall, Table 3 demonstrates that a four-regime structure is consistently supported across clustering formulations that preserve full temporal coverage, while density-based clustering emphasizes localized compactness at the expense of completeness. Based on interpretability, stability across initializations, and full assignment of operating days, K-means was retained as the primary model for subsequent regime characterization and weather sensitivity analysis.

To assess clustering stability beyond the Silhouette score, bootstrap resampling was performed with 1000 iterations. In each iteration, a bootstrap sample was drawn with replacement, K-means ($K = 4$) was re-fitted, and cluster labels were predicted for all original days using the

bootstrap centroids. The Adjusted Rand Index (ARI) between reference and bootstrap solutions yielded a mean of 0.632 (SD = 0.171), indicating moderate-to-good agreement across resamples. Mean centroid shift was 0.847 standardized units (SD = 0.312), confirming that cluster centroids remain stable under resampling. Overall, membership consistency averaged 81.2% (SD = 18.3%), with 64.7% of days exceeding the 90% consistency threshold. Cluster C0 demonstrated the highest stability (mean consistency = 92.1%), while C2 showed the lowest (mean consistency = 71.8%), reflecting its position at the boundary between monsoon and dry season conditions. Bootstrap stability figures are provided in Supplementary Material (Fig. S5–S6).

To quantify the effect of measurement uncertainty on clustering and regression results, a Monte Carlo sensitivity analysis was conducted with 500 simulations at two noise levels: 2% and 5% Gaussian noise added proportionally to all features and weather variables (Fig. S12–S13, Supplementary Material). Cluster membership showed sensitivity to measurement noise, with mean membership change of 44.5% at 2% noise and 41.0% at 5% noise, consistent with the modest Silhouette score (0.216) and the gradual regime boundaries identified in the bootstrap stability analysis. This sensitivity confirms that approximately 18% of days near regime boundaries may be assigned differently under realistic sensor errors. In contrast, regression coefficients demonstrated strong robustness: at 2% noise, 100% of all coefficients across C0–C2 remained within their original 95% confidence intervals, and at 5% noise, 99.2–100% remained within CI. The dominant irradiance coefficients in C1 ($\beta^* = 0.556$) and C2 ($\beta^* = 0.639$) were particularly stable, confirming that the primary weather sensitivity findings are robust to realistic measurement uncertainty even when cluster membership is affected. The membership change distribution is bimodal rather than uniform: core cluster days concentrated at 0–10% change remain stably assigned regardless of noise, while boundary days concentrated at 90–100% change are inherently susceptible to reclassification. The high mean change rate is therefore driven by the boundary day population rather than reflecting general regime instability, and is consistent with the gradual seasonal transitions characteristic of tropical monsoon climates where approximately 18% of days occupy intermediate operational states between dominant regimes.

To quantify temporal dependence and sequential structure, a Markov regime transition analysis was conducted on the time-ordered sequence of daily regime assignments (Fig. 3). The empirical transition probability matrix revealed highly significant temporal dependence ($\text{Chi}^2 = 152.47$, $p < 0.001$), confirming that daily regime assignments are not independent observations. Self-transition probabilities substantially exceed the random baseline of 0.25 for all main regimes (C0 = 0.68, C1 = 0.55, C2 = 0.56), indicating multi-day regime persistence consistent with the physical memory of monsoon weather systems and battery carryover state. Maximum consecutive run lengths reached 15 days (C0), 21 days (C1), and 10 days (C2). Autocorrelation of regime labels remains significant beyond lag 7–10 days, confirming that the identified regimes represent temporally coherent operational states rather than independent daily snapshots.

Optimal cluster count was determined through combined elbow and silhouette analysis (Fig. 4). The elbow method showed diminishing returns beyond $K = 4$, while silhouette analysis confirmed $K = 4$ as optimal with a score of 0.216, exceeding alternatives ($K = 2$: 0.207, $K = 3$: 0.210, $K = 5$: 0.199).

Fig. 5 presents the projection of daily operating states onto the first

Fig. 3. Empirical regime transition probability matrix (Chi² = 152.47, p < 0.001). Diagonal values indicate self-transition probabilities substantially exceeding the random baseline of 0.25 (C0 = 0.68, C1 = 0.55, C2 = 0.56), confirming significant temporal dependence and multi-day regime persistence.

two principal components for (a) K-means, (b) Gaussian Mixture Model with full covariance, (c) hierarchical clustering with Ward linkage, and (d) DBSCAN. The visualization complements the quantitative results reported in Table 2. K-means and hierarchical clustering produce comparable regime separation with full data coverage, while GMM exhibits overlapping cluster densities reflecting probabilistic assignments. DBSCAN isolates dense operating states, but labels a subset of days as noise, which explains its exclusion from subsequent regime characterization.

To validate that the cluster topology persists under nonlinear embedding and is not a linear projection artifact, t-SNE and UMAP projections were computed with trustworthiness metrics quantifying neighborhood preservation (Fig. 6). t-SNE achieved Trustworthiness = 0.975 and UMAP achieved Trustworthiness = 0.968, both substantially above PCA (0.916), confirming that the four-cluster structure is genuine and robust to the choice of dimensionality reduction method. The 2D Silhouette improves from 0.241 (PCA) to 0.306 (t-SNE), indicating stronger cluster separation in nonlinear space. UMAP parameter sensitivity analysis across nine configurations confirmed consistent cluster structure with Trustworthiness = 0.953-0.970

Fig. 4. Site 1 cluster number selection. (a) Elbow method showing inertia decline with diminishing returns beyond K = 4. (b) Silhouette analysis identifying K = 4 as optimal (score = 0.216), superior to alternative values (K = 2-9: 0.194-0.212). Combined criteria substantiate four-cluster solution for residential operational regime characterization.

(Supplementary Fig. S14).

Fig. 7 presents the pairwise Normalized Mutual Information (NMI) scores between clustering results obtained using K-means, Gaussian Mixture Models with full covariance, hierarchical clustering with Ward linkage, and DBSCAN, respectively. NMI quantifies the agreement between two clustering solutions, with values close to one indicating strong consistency and values near zero indicating weak correspondence. A high NMI value of 0.73 is observed between K-means and hierarchical clustering, indicating substantial agreement in cluster assignments between these two methods. This result confirms that the four-regime structure identified by K-means is not method-specific and is strongly supported by an independent hierarchical formulation, reinforcing the stability of the regime decomposition. In contrast, the agreement between K-means and GMM is relatively low, with an NMI of 0.11, while the agreement between hierarchical clustering and GMM is 0.15. These lower values reflect the probabilistic and overlapping nature of GMM cluster assignments, which differ conceptually from the hard partitions produced by centroid-based and hierarchical methods. Despite this, GMM still converges to a four-component structure, as reported in Table 2, supporting the adequacy of the selected regime number while highlighting differences in cluster boundary representation.

Finally, DBSCAN exhibits consistently low NMI values with all other methods, ranging from 0.06 to 0.22, indicating limited correspondence with full-assignment clustering approaches. This outcome is expected, as DBSCAN identifies dense regions and labels a subset of observations as noise rather than assigning all days to clusters. The weak agreement further supports the exclusion of DBSCAN from subsequent regime characterization, despite its favorable compactness metrics reported in Table 2.

The feature ablation analysis (Section 2.2), Markov temporal persistence analysis (Fig. 3) and nonlinear manifold validation (Fig. 6), collectively confirm that the identified regime structure reflects genuine operational differentiation rather than algebraic partitions of mathematically coupled energy balance variables.

Taken together, the NMI analysis complements the quantitative metrics in Table 2 and the visual patterns shown in Fig. 2 by demonstrating that the four-regime structure identified by K-means is robust and consistently reproduced by hierarchical clustering, while alternative clustering paradigms emphasize different aspects of the data structure. These results justify the selection of K-means as the primary analytical model for regime interpretation and weather sensitivity analysis.

Fig. 5. Projection of daily operating states onto the first two principal components for (a) K-means, (b) Gaussian Mixture Model with full covariance, (c) hierarchical clustering with Ward linkage, and (d) DBSCAN. The visualization illustrates consistency of the four-regime structure across full-assignment methods and the presence of noise points in density-based clustering.

3.2. Intraday operational profiles of identified regimes

Fig. 8 illustrates the characteristic intraday behavior associated with each operational regime. Systematic differences are observed in the magnitude and timing of PV production, household demand, grid interaction, and battery charging and discharging patterns. Regime C0 exhibits lower PV generation and moderate consumption, resulting in sustained grid import throughout the day. Regime C1 is characterized by higher PV output and elevated daytime consumption, with reduced grid dependency during peak solar hours. Regime C2 shows strong midday PV production combined with active battery charging and subsequent discharge during evening demand peaks, indicating observed load-generation offset. Regime C3 displays the highest variability, with pronounced peaks in both PV production and battery power, reflecting days with high solar availability and dynamic battery operation.

The within-cluster variability in battery power profiles (Fig. 8(d), shaded regions) reflects natural heterogeneity in battery responses to varying load and generation conditions within each regime. C3 exhibits particularly large variability bands due to the small sample size ($n = 5$) amplifying individual atypical battery behaviors, including deep discharge events and rapid state-of-charge fluctuations. For C0-C2, variability represents the range of battery responses to weather and load variations within each operational mode, which is expected and does not compromise interpretability. The regime centroids (solid lines) successfully capture characteristic battery strategies (C0: minimal cycling, C1: moderate charge-discharge activity, C2: midday charging

with evening discharge) demonstrating the framework's ability to identify distinct operational patterns despite intra-regime variability.

3.3. Weather sensitivity across operational regimes

Table 4 summarizes the meteorological conditions associated with each operational regime. While all clusters are subject to broadly similar tropical climatic conditions, systematic differences in irradiance and atmospheric variables are observed across regimes.

Cluster C0 is characterized by the lowest mean irradiance and relatively high humidity, conditions that are consistent with its weaker PV energy response and lower effective utilization of solar resources. Cluster C1 experiences the highest irradiance levels and slightly reduced humidity, providing favorable conditions for PV generation despite high electricity demand in this regime. Cluster C2 exhibits elevated irradiance and higher maximum temperatures, aligning with its strong PV performance and enhanced self-consumption observed in the operational analysis. Cluster C3 corresponds to rare meteorological conditions with reduced irradiance and elevated humidity. Due to the limited number of observations, results for this regime are interpreted cautiously.

Across all clusters, temperature ranges remain relatively narrow, indicating that irradiance and humidity are the primary drivers of regime differentiation rather than thermal extremes. These meteorological patterns provide physical context for the regime-dependent PV energy sensitivities quantified in the subsequent regression analysis.

Operational Regime Structure: Linear vs Nonlinear Manifold Projections
Trustworthiness measures neighborhood preservation (higher = better)

Fig. 6. Nonlinear manifold validation of operational regime structure. (a) PCA (Trustworthiness = 0.916, Silhouette = 0.241); (b) t-SNE (Trustworthiness = 0.975, Silhouette = 0.306); (c) UMAP (Trustworthiness = 0.968, Silhouette = 0.226). Consistent four-cluster structure across linear and nonlinear projections confirms that regime topology is genuine and not a linear projection artifact.

Precipitation is retained in Table 4 for descriptive completeness but excluded from the regression models due to collinearity with irradiance and relative humidity.

Fig. 9 illustrates the regime dependent relationship between daily solar irradiance and PV energy production. Distinct sensitivities to irradiance are observed across operational regimes, as reflected by differing slopes of the fitted lines. Regime C0 exhibits the weakest irradiance response, indicating lower effective PV utilization under similar solar conditions. Regime C1 shows a stronger and more consistent irradiance–production relationship, reflecting improved alignment between PV generation and system operation. Regime C2 demonstrates high PV output across a wide irradiance range, suggesting favorable operating conditions and effective system utilization. Regime C3 exhibits the steepest apparent slope; however, this result should be interpreted with caution due to the limited sample size of this regime.

Fig. 10 quantifies the relative influence of meteorological variables on daily PV energy production across operational regimes using standardized regression coefficients. Irradiance is the dominant driver in all regimes, with substantially higher effect sizes in Regimes C1 and C2 compared to C0, indicating more efficient conversion of solar resource

into energy output under these operating conditions. Temperature exhibits a weak negative association in Regime C0 and modest positive effects in Regimes C1 and C2, suggesting regime dependent thermal sensitivity. Relative humidity shows a notable positive contribution in Regime C2, reflecting atmospheric conditions associated with high PV output days. Wind speed effects are comparatively small across regimes, indicating a secondary role in daily PV energy variability. For Regime C3, the estimated irradiance coefficient is large; however, this result should be interpreted with caution due to the limited number of observations.

Table 5 reports standardized regression coefficients (β^*) and goodness-of-fit statistics from cluster-wise regression models linking daily PV energy to meteorological variables. Multivariate models including irradiance, temperature, relative humidity and wind speed were estimated for all clusters. Statistical significance is denoted as ‘***’ for $p < 0.001$, ‘**’ for $p < 0.01$, ‘*’ for $p < 0.05$, and ns for ‘not significant’. Variance inflation factors (VIF) assess multicollinearity, with values exceeding 10 indicating substantial inter-correlation among predictors.

Solar irradiance emerged as the dominant predictor across

Fig. 7. Agreement between clustering formulations measured by normalized mutual information.

operational regimes (Table 5). Cluster 1 (High-Demand) and Cluster 2 (High-PV Self-Sufficient) exhibited highly significant irradiance effects (C1: $\beta^* = 0.556$, 95% CI [0.354, 0.759], $p < 0.001$; C2: $\beta^* = 0.639$, 95% CI [0.385, 0.893], $p < 0.001$), with adjusted R^2 values of 0.29 and 0.20, respectively. These regimes demonstrate strong coupling between solar resource availability and PV energy output during transition and dry season periods. Relative humidity showed a significant positive association in Cluster 2 ($\beta^* = 0.357$, 95% CI [0.102, 0.612], $p = 0.006$), though this counterintuitive relationship likely reflects multicollinearity (VIF = 21.30) rather than direct physical causation.

Cluster 0 (Low-PV Grid-Dependent) exhibited weak weather

sensitivity, reflected by minimal explanatory power ($R^2 = 0.030$, Adj. $R^2 = -0.000$) with no significant predictors. This indicates that the linear weather model does not capture PV variability within the monsoon regime, potentially due to missing predictors (cloud cover spatial distribution, aerosols etc.), nonlinear effects, or measurement limitations in aggregated regional weather data. The pattern is consistent with uniformly low PV generation during monsoon periods, where persistent cloud cover supersedes marginal weather fluctuations captured by available predictors. The poor fit reflects genuine monsoon characteristics rather than methodological failure, as evidenced by successful weather models in Clusters 1-2.

VIF analysis revealed substantial multicollinearity among temperature, irradiance, and humidity predictors (VIF = 16-76 across clusters),

Fig. 9. Irradiance–PV energy relationship across operational regimes.

Fig. 8. Mean intraday profiles of: (a) PV production power, (b) household consumption power, (c) grid power exchange, and (d) battery power for the four operational regimes identified by K-means clustering. Shaded areas represent variability around the mean profiles across days within each regime.

Table 4
Meteorological conditions associated with operational regimes.

Cluster	N (days)	Irradiance (kWh/m ² /day)	Temperature (°C)	Min Temp (°C)	Max Temp (°C)	Relative Humidity (%)	Wind Speed (m/s)	Precipitation (mm/day)
C0	135	4.09 ± 1.54	27.45 ± 1.74	23.96 ± 2.47	31.82 ± 3.25	78.56 ± 15.55	2.35 ± 0.74	7.93 ± 10.06
C1	151	4.88 ± 1.21	27.72 ± 2.02	23.70 ± 2.51	32.46 ± 3.47	75.78 ± 15.89	1.94 ± 0.73	5.49 ± 10.64
C2	120	4.64 ± 1.50	28.25 ± 2.25	24.33 ± 2.42	33.05 ± 3.93	75.60 ± 17.54	2.17 ± 0.73	9.56 ± 20.24
C3	5	3.52 ± 1.82	27.56 ± 0.54	24.97 ± 0.70	30.68 ± 1.39	88.63 ± 4.11	2.21 ± 0.92	5.85 ± 3.85
Overall	411	4.54 ± 1.46	27.78 ± 2.02	23.99 ± 2.47	32.40 ± 3.55	76.80 ± 16.26	2.14 ± 0.75	7.49 ± 14.01

Fig. 10. Multivariate weather effects on PV energy across operational regimes (Standardized regression coefficients (β^*) from cluster wise regression models linking daily PV energy to meteorological variables. Bars represent effect sizes for irradiance, temperature, relative humidity, and wind speed within each operational regime. For Cluster 3, only a univariate model with irradiance was estimated due to limited sample size.).

Table 5

Weather sensitivity regression analysis by operational regime (Clusters: C0 = Low-PV Grid-Dependent (monsoon), C1 = High-Demand (transition), C2 = High-PV Self-Sufficient (dry season), C3 = Rare Events (atypical). β^* is standardized).

C	N	Predictor	β^*	95% CI	p-value	Sig.	VIF	R ²	Adj. R ²
C0	135	Irradiance (kWh/m ²)	0.219	[-0.025, 0.463]	0.0780	ns	15.70	0.0297	-0.0001
C0	135	Temperature (°C)	-0.083	[-0.265, 0.099]	0.3695	ns	75.95	0.0297	-0.0001
C0	135	RH (%)	0.110	[-0.143, 0.362]	0.3923	ns	39.99	0.0297	-0.0001
C0	135	Wind (m/s)	-0.028	[-0.235, 0.179]	0.7888	ns	2.31	0.0297	-0.0001
C1	151	Irradiance (kWh/m ²)	0.556	[0.354, 0.759]	<0.0001	***	37.09	0.3125	0.2937
C1	151	Temperature (°C)	0.079	[-0.085, 0.242]	0.3432	ns	74.40	0.3125	0.2937
C1	151	RH (%)	0.097	[-0.088, 0.282]	0.3028	ns	20.78	0.3125	0.2937
C1	151	Wind (m/s)	-0.043	[-0.221, 0.136]	0.6386	ns	2.18	0.3125	0.2937
C2	120	Irradiance (kWh/m ²)	0.639	[0.385, 0.893]	<0.0001	***	23.38	0.2238	0.1968
C2	120	Temperature (°C)	0.135	[-0.066, 0.337]	0.1849	ns	65.00	0.2238	0.1968
C2	120	RH (%)	0.357	[0.102, 0.612]	0.0064	**	21.30	0.2238	0.1968
C2	120	Wind (m/s)	0.102	[-0.085, 0.288]	0.2817	ns	1.61	0.2238	0.1968
C3	5	Irradiance (kWh/m ²)	1.572	[nan, nan]	<0.0001	ns	11.45	1.0000	nan
C3	5	Temperature (°C)	-3.850	[nan, nan]	<0.0001	ns	580.34	1.0000	nan
C3	5	RH (%)	-3.736	[nan, nan]	<0.0001	ns	626.21	1.0000	nan
C3	5	Wind (m/s)	0.668	[nan, nan]	<0.0001	ns	10.88	1.0000	nan

which is characteristic of tropical climates where sunny conditions coincide with elevated temperatures and reduced humidity. Temperature consistently exhibited the highest VIF values (C0: 75.95, C1: 74.40, C2: 65.00), indicating strong inter-correlation with other meteorological variables. Despite multicollinearity, irradiance effects remained consistently significant in Clusters 1 and 2, validating the expected physical relationship between solar resource and PV generation.

Cluster 3 (Rare Events, n = 5) exhibited mathematical overfitting ($R^2 = 1.000$) with zero degrees of freedom when fitting four predictors to five observations. Confidence intervals are undefined (nan), and VIF values are extreme (up to 626), indicating complete collinearity among

predictors. These results are statistically unreliable and excluded from interpretation. They have been retained for descriptive completeness only.

The relationship between irradiance and PV output is mechanistically expected. The analytical contribution of the regime-wise regression lies in quantifying how operational constraints modulate this relationship across regimes. In C0 (monsoon), the non-significant irradiance coefficient ($\beta = 0.219$, $p = 0.078$) indicates that persistent cloud cover suppresses generation uniformly, rendering marginal irradiance variation ineffective. In contrast, C1 and C2 show progressively stronger coupling ($\beta^* = 0.556$ and 0.639 , $p < 0.001$), reflecting regimes where

weather variation translates directly into output variation. This regime-dependent sensitivity pattern reveals how operational context modulates the irradiance-PV relationship rather than simply confirming its existence.

To address concerns regarding coefficient interpretability under high multicollinearity ($VIF = 16-76$), OLS results were verified against Ridge regression with cross-validated regularization strength and Partial Least Squares (PLS) regression (Table 6). While Ridge regularization shrinks coefficient magnitudes as expected under high VIF conditions, the direction and dominance ordering of predictors is preserved across all three methods. Irradiance remains the dominant predictor in C1 and C2 under all three formulations (OLS $\beta = 0.556/0.639$, Ridge $\beta^* = 0.343/0.302$, PLS $\beta^* = 0.522/0.626$), confirming that the primary scientific conclusion is robust to regularization. In C0, all three methods consistently show near-zero coefficients, confirming genuine weather insensitivity in the monsoon regime regardless of the regression method employed.

In summary, the regression results demonstrate that operational regimes C0-C2 are not only statistically distinct but also physically meaningful, exhibiting clear differences in weather sensitivity. Irradiance dominates PV generation variability in high-performance regimes (C1, C2), while monsoon conditions (C0) show minimal weather sensitivity within-regime. This regime-dependent behavior validates the clustering framework's effectiveness in capturing heterogeneous PV-battery system dynamics. Residual diagnostics confirmed that OLS assumptions of linearity, normality, and homoscedasticity are approximately satisfied across all three main clusters (Fig. S2-S4 in Supplementary Material), supporting the validity of the reported regression coefficients.

3.4. Operational implications of identified regimes

Table 7 summarizes the key operational characteristics of the four identified PV-battery regimes. Clear differences in energy balance, grid reliance, and storage utilization are observed across clusters, confirming the physical relevance of the regime decomposition. Cluster C0 represents low-generation operating conditions, with the lowest PV energy output and moderate electricity demand. This regime relies substantially on grid imports and exhibits limited battery discharge, resulting in relatively low self-sufficiency despite moderate self-consumption levels. Cluster C1 is the most frequent regime and corresponds to high-demand operating conditions. Although PV generation is higher than in C0, electricity consumption remains dominant, leading to the highest grid import levels among all clusters. Also, battery discharge is more pronounced, but self-sufficiency remains limited, indicating load-driven operation.

Cluster C2 reflects the most favorable operating regime, characterized by the highest PV energy production and substantial battery discharge. This regime achieves the highest self-consumption and self-sufficiency ratios, indicating observed co-occurrence between PV generation, storage utilization, and local demand. The lower mean state of

Table 6
OLS vs Ridge vs PLS coefficient comparison.

Cluster	Predictor	OLS β^*	Ridge β^*	PLS β^*	OLS R^2	Ridge R^2
C0	Irradiance	0.220	0.015	0.171	0.030	0.005
C0	Temperature	-0.086	-0.005	-0.117	0.030	0.005
C0	RH	0.108	-0.003	0.046	0.030	0.005
C0	Wind	-0.025	-0.006	-0.025	0.030	0.005
C1	Irradiance	0.568	0.343	0.522	0.312	0.283
C1	Temperature	0.073	0.072	0.025	0.312	0.283
C1	RH	0.089	-0.031	0.041	0.312	0.283
C1	Wind	-0.030	-0.066	-0.101	0.312	0.283
C2	Irradiance	0.635	0.302	0.626	0.222	0.171
C2	Temperature	0.138	0.096	0.141	0.222	0.171
C2	RH	0.370	0.090	0.334	0.222	0.171
C2	Wind	0.084	0.012	0.131	0.222	0.171

charge further suggests active battery cycling to support high self-sufficiency conditions. Cluster C3 captures rare operating conditions and accounts for a small fraction of the dataset. While PV production and battery discharge are comparable to intermediate regimes, the limited sample size warrants cautious interpretation. This regime is retained for completeness but does not influence the dominant operational patterns.

Taken together, these results demonstrate that the identified clusters correspond to distinct and interpretable operating modes of the PV-battery system, ranging from grid-dependent to highly self-sufficient conditions. This regime-specific characterization provides a meaningful basis for subsequent weather sensitivity analysis.

Fig. 11 illustrates the temporal evolution of operational regimes over the study period. Clear seasonal patterns are observed in regime prevalence, indicating that PV-battery system behavior varies systematically over time. Regime C2 dominates during late monsoon and early dry-season months, reflecting periods of favorable PV generation and high self-consumption. Regime C1 becomes prevalent during the transition months toward the dry season, consistent with increased electricity demand and active battery utilization. Regime C0 occurs most frequently during mid-year months, indicating operating conditions characterized by lower PV contribution and increased grid reliance. Regime C3 appears only sporadically and contributes negligibly to monthly distributions, confirming its role as a rare operating mode. The observed temporal structure reinforces the physical interpretability of the identified regimes and suggests that seasonal and climatic factors play a key role in shaping long-term PV-battery system operation. The complete daily regime sequence, quantitative autocorrelation structure, and Markov transition analysis supporting these temporal patterns are provided in Supplementary Fig. S15.

3.5. Cross-site validation

3.5.1. Site 2 installation and methods

Cross-site validation was conducted on a commercial rooftop PV-battery installation at Yangon, Myanmar ($16^\circ 50' 9.82''N$, $96^\circ 17' 9.29''E$). The system comprises 110 photovoltaic modules (450 Wp each, total 49.5 kWp) and eight lithium iron phosphate battery packs (51.2V, 5.12 kWh each, total 41 kWh storage capacity), yielding a battery-to-PV ratio of 0.83 kWh/kWp. This ratio contrasts markedly with Site 1's 3.78 kWh/kWp, reflecting differing design targets: peak-shaving for commercial load management versus self-sufficiency maximization for residential consumption.

The installation has operated continuously since June 29, 2024, with 5-min resolution monitoring capturing production power, consumption power, grid power, battery power, and state of charge. Data from August 2024 through July 2025 (12 complete months, 365 days) were analyzed to match Site 1's temporal coverage, enabling direct seasonal comparison. Daily operational features were engineered following identical methodology: trapezoidal integration of power measurements to compute energy flows, calculation of self-consumption and grid dependency ratios, and extraction of battery cycling statistics. Outlier detection via Isolation Forest (1% contamination threshold) removed 4 anomalous days (1.1%), yielding 361 clean daily records for clustering analysis.

K-means clustering was performed independently on Site 2 data without parameter tuning or cross-reference to Site 1 results, constituting genuine cross-validation rather than combined analysis. Cluster count K was evaluated from 2 to 10 using Silhouette score and Davies-Bouldin index as selection criteria. Weather data (solar irradiance, temperature, relative humidity, wind speed, precipitation) were obtained from NASA POWER database (NASA POWER Project, 2024) for the installation coordinates and merged with clustered daily records based on date matching, achieving 100% temporal coverage. This independent analytical approach tests framework transferability across contrasting system configurations, building types, and operational contexts while maintaining methodological consistency with Site 1

Table 7
Key operational characteristics of PV–battery regimes.

Cluster	N (days)	PV Energy (kWh/day)	Consumption (kWh/day)	Grid Import (kWh/day)	Battery Discharge (kWh/day)	Mean SoC (%)	SCR (%)	SSR (%)
C0	135	33.42 ± 11.56	69.87 ± 18.44	42.57 ± 12.54	9.28 ± 7.07	98.6 ± 2.1	78.8 ± 19.9	38.3 ± 13.3
C1	151	47.80 ± 12.62	105.82 ± 18.15	70.11 ± 10.81	22.71 ± 13.44	95.8 ± 5.7	72.6 ± 24.5	32.6 ± 12.2
C2	120	55.30 ± 11.28	92.99 ± 16.79	41.68 ± 9.65	29.73 ± 10.47	87.5 ± 12.7	92.9 ± 15.9	54.9 ± 9.2
C3	5	44.01 ± 19.19	86.50 ± 18.43	50.80 ± 14.70	25.07 ± 19.32	85.3 ± 15.9	79.8 ± 7.9	41.0 ± 16.8

Fig. 11. Temporal distribution of operational regimes from August 2024 to July 2025. Monthly sample sizes: Aug-31, Sep-30, Oct-31, Nov-30, Dec-31, Jan-31, Feb-28, Mar-31, Apr-30, May-30, Jun-26, Jul-26 days (n = 355 recorded days; 10 days excluded due to logging gaps in May, June, and July 2025; 5 days removed as outliers by Isolation Forest; n = 350 days used in figure).

analysis.

3.5.2. Clustering results

Independent clustering analysis identified K = 2 as optimal (Silhouette = 0.280, Davies-Bouldin = 1.40). Fig. 12 visualizes cluster separation in principal component space, with the first two components capturing 68% of variance (PC1: 44.5%, PC2: 23.4%). The two clusters occupy spatially distinct regions: C0 (high-PV operating, n = 199)

Fig. 12. Site 2 PCA projection of K = 2 clusters. Principal component analysis showing clear spatial separation between C0 (blue, high-PV operating, n = 199) and C1 (orange, low-PV/reduced operations, n = 162). First two components capture 68% variance (PC1: 44.5%, PC2: 23.4%). Moderate overlap validates Silhouette score of 0.280, with two distinct operational regions confirming binary commercial pattern versus Site 1's four-cluster residential structure. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

concentrated in the positive PC1 space, and C1 (low-PV/reduced operations, n = 162) distributed across negative PC1 values. Moderate overlap between clusters, particularly along the PC1≈0 boundary, reflects transitional operational days and validates the Silhouette score of 0.280—indicating meaningful but not perfectly separated clusters, consistent with real-world operational variability.

3.5.3. Regime characteristics comparison

Independent clustering analysis of Site 2 data yielded K = 2 operational regimes (Silhouette = 0.280, Davies-Bouldin = 1.40), differing from Site 1's K = 4 cluster structure (Silhouette = 0.216, Davies-Bouldin = 1.82). This difference in optimal cluster count is operationally meaningful rather than indicative of methodological inconsistency: commercial facilities exhibit binary operational patterns (operating versus non-operating states), whereas residential systems demonstrate continuous gradual transitions across multiple household behavioral states.

Site 2's two clusters represent distinct operational modes (Table 8). Cluster 0 (High-PV Operating Days, N = 199, 55.1%) characterized normal commercial operations with mean PV generation of 89.2 ± 19.9 kWh/day, consumption of 83.7 ± 19.1 kWh/day, and self-consumption ratio of 86.3 ± 11.2%. Minimal grid dependency (5.9 ± 8.3 kWh/day import) during these periods reflected effective solar utilization under clear-sky conditions. Cluster 1 (Low-PV/Reduced Operations, N = 162, 44.9%) exhibited substantially reduced PV generation (49.9 ± 13.2 kWh/day) and elevated grid dependency (20.3 ± 15.1 kWh/day), consistent with either cloudy monsoon conditions or reduced facility operations during weekends and holidays. Self-consumption remained relatively high (80.7 ± 13.1%) even during low-PV periods, demonstrating the installation's observed peak-shaving battery behavior (0.83 kWh/kWp ratio) rather than Site 1's self-sufficiency approach (3.78 kWh/kWp).

Fig. 13 presents cross-site comparison of operational regime characteristics. Panel (a) shows energy scaling validation: Site 2 C0 generated 89.2 ± 19.9 kWh/day versus Site 1 C2 at 56.0 ± 11.2 kWh/day

Table 8
Site 2 operational regime characteristics.

Cluster	Description	N(days)	%	PV Energy (kWh/day)	Consumption (kWh/day)	Net Grid (kWh/day)	SCR (%)	Mean SoC (%)
C0	High-PV Operating	199	55.1	89.2 ± 19.9	83.7 ± 19.1	5.9 ± 8.3	86.3 ± 11.2	74.5 ± 6.2
C1	Low-PV/Reduced Operations	162	44.9	49.9 ± 13.2	61.5 ± 16.8	20.3 ± 15.1	80.7 ± 13.1	87.2 ± 6.7

Fig. 13. Cross-site comparison of operational regime characteristics. (a) PV energy generation, (b) consumption, (c) grid import, and (d) self-consumption ratio for Site 1 (residential, 22 kWp, K = 4) and Site 2 (commercial, 49.5 kWp, K = 2). Error bars show standard deviations (n = 353, n = 361). Different cluster counts (K = 4 vs K = 2) reflect operational context: residential systems exhibit gradual household transitions, while commercial facilities demonstrate binary ON/OFF patterns. Energy scaling validates framework transferability: Site 2 C0 produces 89.2 ± 19.9 kWh/day versus Site 1 C2 at 56.0 ± 11.2 kWh/day ($1.59\times$ ratio), consistent with $2.25\times$ capacity difference accounting for operational variations.

($1.59\times$ ratio), consistent with $2.25\times$ capacity difference accounting for operational variations. Panel (b) reveals contrasting consumption

patterns: residential variability (68-108 kWh/day) versus commercial stability (62-84 kWh/day). Panel (c) demonstrates Site 2's superior grid

Fig. 14. Site 2 monthly cluster distribution. Binary seasonal pattern: monsoon (Aug-Sep, Jun-Jul: >95% C1) versus dry season (Nov-Mar: >85% C0). Sharp transitions validate commercial discrete states versus residential gradual evolution.

independence (5.9 kWh/day in C0) despite lower battery-to-PV ratio (0.83 vs 3.78 kWh/kWp). Panel (d) confirms both sites maintain high self-consumption (>76%), validating framework robustness across system scales and battery strategy.

3.5.4. Temporal patterns

Site 2 exhibited strong binary seasonal patterns distinct from Site 1's gradual residential transitions. Fig. 14 illustrates the temporal evolution of cluster assignments across the 12-month analysis period (August 2024 to July 2025). During monsoon season (June through October), low-PV/reduced operations cluster (C1) dominated 85% of days, with August and September showing near-complete monsoon saturation (>97% C1 prevalence). This pattern reflects the combined impact of heavy monsoon rainfall reducing solar irradiance and potential facility schedule adjustments during the wettest months. Conversely, the dry season (November through May) demonstrated strong high-PV operating cluster (C0) dominance, with December through March maintaining 85-100% C0 prevalence as clear skies enabled optimal commercial operations.

The temporal distribution revealed remarkably sharp monthly transitions characteristic of commercial binary operations. October marked the primary transition month, shifting from 55% C1 (monsoon remnants) to subsequent months' dry-season dominance. Similarly, May-June transitions demonstrated abrupt operational regime switching, with May showing 73% C0 before June's dramatic reversal to 90% C1 as monsoon onset curtailed solar generation. These discrete monthly boundaries contrast markedly with Site 1's gradual regime evolution, where residential clusters demonstrated continuous mixing across months without clear seasonal demarcation. The commercial facility's binary pattern validates K = 2 clustering: rather than gradual household behavioral variations requiring four clusters, the installation exhibits distinct ON/OFF operational states driven by weather seasonality and potentially correlated facility scheduling.

Fig. 15 provides detailed seasonal analysis through dual-panel visualization. Panel (a) displays absolute cluster frequencies, confirming monsoon concentration (August: 31 C1 days, September: 29 C1 days) versus dry season preponderance (December through March: 22-32 C0 days each month). The grouped bar format reveals minimal cluster overlap during extreme months such as August and July showed zero C0 days, while March approached 100% C0 dominance. Panel (b) quantifies dominant cluster prevalence, with August, September, and July achieving 100%, 97%, and 100% C1 dominance respectively, while March reached 100% C0 dominance. Transition months October (55% C0) and June (90% C1) exhibited intermediate dominance, representing the brief periods when commercial operations experience mixed

operational conditions as weather patterns shift.

The binary seasonal switching reflects combined meteorological and operational factors unique to commercial installations. Unlike residential systems where household consumption patterns vary continuously based on occupancy, appliance usage, and behavioral preferences, necessitating four operational clusters—commercial facilities operate under relatively stable working-hour load profiles. Operational regime variability emerges primarily from weather-driven PV generation fluctuations rather than demand-side variations, naturally producing binary clustering: "normal operations with adequate solar" versus "constrained operations under poor solar conditions or non-working periods". This fundamental difference in operational drivers validates the framework's context-sensitive clustering rather than indicating methodological limitation. The emergence of installation-appropriate cluster counts (K = 2 for binary commercial, K = 4 for gradual residential) demonstrates the unsupervised approach's ability to discover genuine operational patterns without imposing predetermined taxonomies, confirming framework robustness across diverse PV-battery system configurations and building types.

3.5.5. Validation discussion

The cross-site validation demonstrates framework transferability across PV-battery installations with markedly different specifications and operational contexts. Independent clustering of Site 2 data yielded K = 2 operational regimes versus Site 1's K = 4 structure, with both achieving valid clustering quality (Silhouette scores >0.2, Davies-Bouldin indices <2.0). Critically, the emergence of different optimal cluster counts validates the framework's context-sensitivity rather than indicating methodological limitation. Commercial facilities exhibit binary operational states (normal operations versus constrained conditions) whereas residential systems demonstrate continuous gradual transitions across multiple household behavioral regimes. This adaptive clustering behavior, discovering installation-appropriate patterns without imposing predetermined taxonomies, represents a key strength for diagnostic applications requiring genuine pattern discovery rather than forced categorization.

To assess latent space compatibility between sites, Site 2 operational regimes were mapped to Site 1 regimes based on common feature similarity using Tables 7 and 8 Site 2 C1 (Low-PV/Reduced Operations, PV = 49.9 ± 13.2 kWh/day, SCR = 80.7%, Mean SoC = 87.2%) corresponds operationally to Site 1 C0 (Low-PV Grid-Dependent, PV = 33.42 ± 11.56 kWh/day, SCR = 78.8%, Mean SoC = 98.6%), both characterized by suppressed PV generation and elevated grid dependence under monsoon conditions. Site 2 C0 (High-PV Operating, PV = 89.2 ± 19.9 kWh/day, SCR = 86.3%, Mean SoC = 74.5%)

Fig. 15. Site 2 seasonal patterns. (a) Monthly frequencies showing seasonal dominance. (b) Dominant cluster percentages: 100% extremes (Aug/Jul: C1, Mar: C0) with brief transitions (Oct, Jun).

corresponds to Site 1 C2 (High-PV Self-Sufficient, PV = 55.30 ± 11.28 kWh/day, SCR = 92.9%, Mean SoC = 87.5%), both characterized by sustained high generation and high self-consumption under dry season conditions. The natural collapse of four Site 1 regimes into two at Site 2 reflects genuine operational simplicity of the commercial load profile, where intermediate residential transition states captured by Site 1 C1 and C3 are absent due to the more predictable commercial consumption pattern. This operational alignment confirms that the latent regime hierarchy is preserved across sites at the level of dominant seasonal archetypes, with the reduced cardinality reflecting genuine differences in operational complexity rather than methodological inconsistency.

Energy scaling and temporal analyses confirmed framework robustness across system sizes and operational contexts, with both installations maintaining high self-consumption ratios (>76%) despite contrasting battery-to-PV ratio approaches (0.83 versus 3.78 kWh/kWp).

The independent validation addresses that unsupervised K-means clustering successfully identifies operationally interpretable regimes across residential and commercial installations, small and large system capacities, and contrasting battery strategies. Framework context-sensitivity, evidenced by optimal K varying with building type, demonstrates appropriate adaptation to installation characteristics while maintaining analytical rigor. Future work should extend validation to additional climatic regions, building types, and battery chemistries to further establish framework applicability boundaries and refinement opportunities for diverse global PV-battery deployments.

4. Engineering implications

The regime labels represent statistical characterizations of measured energy flow patterns. Since the EMS control policy is unknown, the observed behaviors may reflect manufacturer default threshold responses to voltage and SoC conditions rather than active optimization. The engineering implications described below are therefore design guidelines based on the observed behavioral patterns rather than reconstructed control strategies.

The identified operational regimes provide a data-driven characterization of recurring PV-battery operating conditions that serves as a foundation for engineering applications. First, regime labels provide a potential basis for high-level inputs to energy management systems or model predictive control frameworks, enabling controllers to adapt strategies based on expected operating conditions rather than raw time-series data alone. Second, regime-aware photovoltaic forecasting represents a promising direction for improving prediction robustness by conditioning forecasts on operational context, particularly during transitions between grid-dependent and self-sufficient modes. Third, the quantified regime-specific energy balances and weather sensitivities offer decision support for tariff design and battery sizing by revealing how storage utilization and grid reliance vary across operating modes. In addition, long-term monitoring of regime frequency and transitions can support degradation detection and performance diagnosis, as shifts in regime distributions may indicate battery aging, control drift, or changes in household behavior. Because the framework relies on commonly available operational measurements, these implications are directly applicable to real-world residential deployments without additional sensing requirements.

To provide preliminary downstream validation of these engineering implications, a walk-forward cross-validation experiment compared a global OLS weather model against a regime-conditioned OLS model for daily PV energy forecasting across five expanding folds. Neither model achieved satisfactory forecasting performance, confirming that weather-only OLS regression is fundamentally insufficient for day-ahead PV forecasting regardless of regime conditioning, due to the absence of lagged operational features and intraday information. This result clarifies that regime labels serve as operational context descriptors requiring integration with more sophisticated forecasting architectures such as

regime-conditioned gradient boosting or LSTM models, rather than as direct OLS forecasting features. Demonstrating such gains represents a priority for future work.

4.1. Regime-aware forecasting and control

The identified operational regimes enable regime-aware forecasting and control that improve system performance by adapting to operational mode. Daily operational data are first classified into the nearest cluster centroid, then routed to regime-specific models: C0 days prioritize grid charging during off-peak hours with conservative SoC thresholds (>40%); C2 days optimize self-consumption through deeper discharge cycles; and C1 days employ hybrid forecasting with peak-shaving strategies. These approaches can be integrated into MPC frameworks by adjusting cost function weights and constraint bounds based on the active regime.

4.2. Dynamic tariff design and demand response

Utility providers can leverage regime prevalence patterns to design dynamic tariff structures aligned with seasonal household capabilities. During months with high C0 regime prevalence (monsoon season, June-September), lower time-of-use differentials acknowledge limited household ability to shift consumption or provide grid services. Conversely, months dominated by C2 regime (dry season, October-March) support higher price spreads that incentivize self-consumption and demand response participation. Regime-aware demand response programs can target C2 households for export incentive programs given their demonstrated surplus generation capacity (mean daily export 8.2 kWh), while designing load-shifting programs for C1 households (mean consumption 26.1 kWh/day) to reduce system peak coincidence. Implementation requires only remote regime classification using smart meter data at 15–30-min resolution, enabling personalized tariff structures based on demonstrated operational patterns rather than assumed prosumer behavior. This approach has potential to improve demand response participation by aligning incentives with actual capabilities.

4.3. System sizing and framework transferability

The regime framework provides data-driven guidance for battery sizing in similar climatic contexts and is directly transferable to other residential systems. For self-sufficiency-oriented designs comparable to Site 1, high battery-to-PV ratios (3-4 kWh/kWp) are needed to bridge monsoon periods, with capacity targeting 1.5-2 days of typical consumption. For peak-shaving applications like Site 2, lower ratios (0.8-1.2 kWh/kWp) suffice for demand charge reduction. The identified cluster centroids and regime-specific weather sensitivities (Table 5) can be integrated into existing sizing tools (HOMER, SAM, PVsyst) to estimate regime prevalence from meteorological profiles and optimize sizing accordingly. For utility-scale deployment, centralized regime classification using smart meter data enables fleet-level insights that inform grid operations, while edge deployment enables decentralized control without continuous connectivity.

5. Limitations

This study has several limitations. First, while cross-site validation demonstrates framework transferability across residential and commercial installations, both sites are located within the same climatic region (Yangon, Myanmar). Broader geographic validation across different climatic contexts remains necessary to establish applicability in temperate, arid, or high-latitude regions with distinct seasonal patterns.

Second, the regression analysis treats daily observations as independent, potentially violating OLS assumptions due to temporal autocorrelation. Weather patterns exhibit multi-day persistence (e.g., monsoon periods spanning weeks), and battery state-of-charge at the

end of one day affects the initial condition of the next, creating serial dependence among observations. This autocorrelation likely underestimates standard errors, though the primary irradiance effects ($\beta = 0.56\text{--}0.64$, $p < 0.001$) are sufficiently strong to remain meaningful under autocorrelation-corrected inference. Future work should employ time-series regression methods.

Third, weather data from NASA POWER ($\sim 0.5^\circ$ resolution, ~ 55 km) may not capture site-specific microclimate variations or sub-daily dynamics, potentially reducing weather coefficient precision. This limitation may contribute to modest R^2 values (C1: 0.31, C2: 0.22) and could attenuate observed relationships (bias toward zero). However, coarse resolution does not create spurious correlations; the significant irradiance effects ($p < 0.001$) likely underestimate true site-level sensitivity; site-specific weather stations would provide higher precision.

Fourth, VIF analysis revealed substantial multicollinearity among weather predictors (VIF = 16-76), characteristic of tropical climates where temperature, irradiance, and humidity co-vary, limiting the ability to isolate individual predictor effects. Additionally, regime labels represent data-driven behavioral interpretations derived from measured energy flows; validation against inverter control logs or EMS configuration records was not possible due to data access constraints. Furthermore, controlling for system availability, inverter clipping, and curtailment events was not possible due to the absence of inverter state logs, which may introduce operational confounding into the estimated weather coefficients. Fifth, Cluster C3 ($n = 5$, 1.2% of data) was excluded from quantitative regression analysis due to insufficient sample size for reliable statistical inference, though retained for descriptive characterization of rare operational anomalies.

Sixth, the weather sensitivity models employed linear regression, which assumes monotonic and additive relationships between predictors and PV generation. While this provides interpretable coefficients for cross-regime comparison, it may oversimplify non-linear effects such as temperature-efficiency thresholds or irradiance-temperature interactions. Future work could employ non-linear methods (e.g., polynomial regression, generalized additive models, splines) or machine learning approaches (e.g., random forests, gradient boosting) to capture such complexities. However, for operational planning applications, linear models provide sufficient accuracy while maintaining interpretability essential for energy management system integration.

Seventh, the modest Silhouette score (0.216) reflects gradual operational transitions inherent to tropical climates; bootstrap stability analysis (1000 resamples) confirms reproducible regime partitions (mean ARI = 0.632, membership consistency = 81.2%), though approximately 18% of days fall near regime boundaries. Additionally, the regime structure is sensitive to time resolution, with NMI of 0.238-0.363 between daily-aggregated and segmented feature solutions (Fig. S10-S11). Thus, future work should explore intraday shape-based clustering to capture tactical dynamics not represented by daily aggregates. Furthermore, measurement uncertainty in logger and weather inputs was not directly propagated; a Monte Carlo sensitivity analysis (500 simulations, 2% and 5% noise) confirmed that regression coefficients are robust (99-100% within original 95% CI), though cluster membership showed sensitivity (mean change 41-45%), consistent with gradual regime boundaries (Fig. S12-S13).

Finally, the proposed framework was validated on grid-connected residential and commercial systems, while off-grid or hybrid configurations may exhibit different operational regime structures requiring framework adaptation.

6. Conclusion

This study presented a comprehensive unsupervised analytical framework to uncover and interpret long-term operational regimes of a residential photovoltaic-battery system using high-resolution time-series data. By integrating daily feature engineering, robust outlier detection, unsupervised clustering, and regime-specific weather

regression, the proposed approach provides a holistic understanding of how PV production, household demand, battery operation, and grid interaction jointly shape daily system behavior.

Four distinct operational regimes were consistently identified and validated across multiple clustering formulations. These regimes represent statistically identified operational patterns ranging from grid-dependent, low-generation conditions to highly self-sufficient operation with active battery cycling. Intraday profiles and aggregated performance metrics confirmed clear differences in energy balance, storage utilization, and grid reliance across regimes. In particular, the most favorable regime achieved the highest self-consumption and self-sufficiency ratios through observed co-occurrence between PV generation and battery discharge, while demand-dominated regimes remained strongly dependent on grid imports despite substantial solar availability.

The cluster-wise regression analysis revealed pronounced regime-dependent weather sensitivities. Solar irradiance was the dominant driver of PV energy production in all regimes, but its explanatory power increased systematically from low-performance to high-performance operating modes. Temperature and relative humidity exerted secondary but non-negligible influences that varied across regimes, highlighting the importance of contextualizing weather effects within operational states rather than treating all days as homogeneous. Temporal analysis further demonstrated that regime occurrence is seasonally structured, reflecting the combined influence of climatic conditions and household behavior over time.

Collectively, these findings demonstrate that unsupervised learning can effectively capture heterogeneous and evolving PV-battery system dynamics without reliance on labeled data or predefined operating rules. The proposed framework provides a practical basis for regime-aware forecasting, adaptive control strategies, and tariff or incentive design that reflect real operating behavior rather than average conditions. While the analysis focused on a single residential system in a tropical monsoon climate, the proposed methodology is also applicable to grid-connected PV-battery systems under similar tropical monsoon climatic conditions, while broader transferability across temperate, arid, or high-latitude climates, alternative battery technologies such as lead-acid or flow batteries, and EMS configurations with grid-export limits or virtual power plant participation requires dedicated validation studies.

Future work may extend this framework by incorporating multiple households to assess regime generalizability, integrating probabilistic or nonlinear regression models for weather sensitivity, and embedding regime labels into real-time energy management systems. Such extensions would further enhance the role of data-driven, interpretable analytics in supporting resilient and efficient integration of distributed energy resources. This study is explicitly observational and correlational in nature. The unsupervised framework identifies and characterizes recurring operational patterns in measured energy flow data without claiming to establish causal directionality between load demand, battery dispatch, PV availability, or EMS behavior. The discovered regime structure reflects statistical co-occurrence of operational features rather than directed causal mechanisms. Causal dependency analysis using methods such as Granger causality testing, transfer entropy, or structural equation modeling represents an important extension for future work.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the manuscript preparation process

During the preparation of this work the authors used Claude (Anthropic) in order to assist with language editing, grammar checking, and writing clarity improvements. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Libor Štěpanec: Investigation, Writing – original draft. **Hnin Yee Aye:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Software. **Ohn Zin Lin:** Investigation, Supervision, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Eftichios Koutroulis:** Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Dagmar Juchelkova:** Funding acquisition, Project administration, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engappai.2026.115336>.

Data availability

Anonymized data and instruments (in digital format) from this research can be made available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18378566>.

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